

Synthesis, characterization, optical and dielectric studies of layered $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ oxide material

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Abstract : Molten flux has been used as an efficient and low temperature method to synthesize $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ using KOH as a flux at a temperature of 400 °C. The products were characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transformer infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), Scanning electron microscope (SEM) and UV-Visible diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS). X-Ray diffraction pattern confirmed the formation of single phase $K_{0.5}CoO_2$. SEM image indicates the obtained samples are diffused micro porous sphere like morphology and its grain size will be in the range of 100–300 nm. Optical properties of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ ceramic shows an energy band gap in the range of 2.50 eV. The dielectric studies of layered $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ have AC-conductivity observed for the frequency range from 50 Hz to 5 MHz and also as the function of temperature from room temperature to 623 K indicates the space charge polarization contributes the conduction mechanism.

Keywords : Oxide, semiconductor, molten flux, dielectric property.

Introduction

The layered potassium cobalt oxides have been used as electrical, magnetic and superconducting material. $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ is a material widely used as magneto-optic materials¹⁻⁵. In recent years, the report has been investigated the feasibility of a low temperature technique as molten salt synthesis (MSS). Solid state method requires repeated mechanical mixing and extensive heat treatment at high temperatures to achieve the desired phase purity. It has been accepted that the wet-chemical process offers advantages of good mixing of the starting materials and excellent chemical homogeneity of the final product. MSS has been considered as a good technological process for preparing inorganic materials as well as where the synthetic temperature can be greatly lowered, and the diffusion speeds of reacting constituents can be obviously accelerated due to the incorporation of salt medium. So products generally possess a good crystalline and different morphology^{6,7}. In the present investigation report one step synthesis of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ by molten flux technique as a short time duration process and studied its optical and dielectric properties. The optical band gap of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ is 2.5 eV behave as semiconducting material. AC-conductivity observed for the function of temperature from room temperature to 673 K indicates the polarization con-

tributes the conduction mechanism and activation energy $E_a = 0.99$ eV can be obtained from dielectric studies.

Experimental

Preparation of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$:

Co_3O_4 and KOH are analytical grade reagent used without further purification. Polycrystalline samples $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ have been prepared by molten flux synthesis. The cobalt oxide powder was added to the flux KOH in a recrystallized alumina crucible and then sintering the crucible at 400 °C in the air for 5 h after the reaction was finished then slowly cooled to room temperature. The black flakes were separated from the flux by washing in hot distilled water repeatedly then dried at room temperature.

Results and discussion

The product was characterized by X-ray diffraction technique (XRD, Bruker D8 Advance, by $CuK\alpha$ radiation, $k\alpha = 1.5406$ Å). Fig. 1(a) shows the XRD pattern of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ was obtained as single phase rhombo-hedral crystal system and its lattice parameters are $a = b = c = 2.5257$ Å. Using the XRD diffraction data, the crystallite sizes of samples were able to be estimated using the Scherrer eq. (1),

$$D = K\lambda/\beta \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

In this equation, D is the crystallite size (nm); K is the so-called shape factor, which usually takes a value of about 0.9; λ is the X-ray wavelength; β the full width at half maximum of the diffraction peak and θ is the diffraction angle. Since the peak from the (003) plane is the most intense among all of the planes of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$. This diffraction was selected to calculate the average crystallite size as 100–300 nm.

Fig. 1(b) shows the FTIR spectrum of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ in KBr matrix. There are peaks at 570, 730 and 870 cm^{-1} due to asymmetric stretching and bending vibrations of Co-O and K-O groups. The surface morphology and chemical composition was determined with an EDX analyzer attached with a (HRSEM FEI Inspect F50) instrument. Fig. 1(c) shows the HRSEM image of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ at low and high magnifications, respectively. From micrograph observations, it can be seen that the sample shown a micro porous spherical morphology. Fig. 1(d) shows the energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDX) used to quantify the elements exist in the sample by taking a selective portion of SEM image in the form of peaks.

Fig. 1. (a) XRD pattern of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$, (b) FTIR pattern of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$, (c) HRSEM images of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ and (d) EDX of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$.

Optical band gap obtained by using Jasco V-670-UV-Visible diffused reflectance spectrometer. Fig. 2(a) shows the optical property of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ was studied by UV-Visible DRS spectroscopy. The spectra recorded was in the range of 200–800 nm at room temperature. The graph was a plot between absorption versus wavelength gives the absorption edge (λ) and it was 238, 349 and 388 nm. In order to calculate the optical band gap of sample by using Tauc's relation [eq. (2)],

$$(\alpha h\nu)^n = A(h\nu - E_g) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2(b) shows the graph was drawn between $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ where α and $h\nu$ denote the absorption coefficient, photon energy respectively and by extrapolating the curve to photon energy axis and hence it shows the band gap E_g is found to be 2.5 eV. The optical absorption plot shows energy band gap vary due to the ligand to metal charge transfer (LMCT) takes place from O^{2-} to Co^{3+} . Hence d-d charge transfer takes place in the system it shows p-type semiconducting material.

Fig. 2. (a) UV-Visible absorbance spectra of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ and (b) band gap estimation by DRS pattern of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$.

LCR meter (HIOKI 3532-50 LCR meter HITESTER) was used to carry dielectric studies in the frequency range from 50 Hz to 5 MHz for variation of temperature. The control, measurements and analyses were maintained through the computer with indigenously developed software. $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ ceramic was pelletized using a hydraulic press technique employing a pressure of 7 tons and it compressed to form a pellet was 12 mm in diameter and 1 mm in thickness. The pellet was finely polished by electronic grade silver paints were applied on top and bottom faces of pellet to make a capacitor. The dielectric constant (ϵ') is calculated from the eq. (3),

$$\epsilon' = ct/\epsilon_0 A \quad (3)$$

where C is the capacitance obtained from the analysis, t is the thickness of the pellet, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of the free space, A is the area of the pellet⁸. The ac conductivity is calculated from the eqs. (4, 5 and 6),

$$\sigma_{ac} = \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon' \tan \delta \quad (4)$$

$$\omega = 2\pi f \quad (5)$$

where f is the applied ac frequency. The activation energy is obtained from the graph σ_{ac} versus inverse of temperature in Kelvin.

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(E_a/kT) \quad (6)$$

where k is Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature.

Fig. 3(a) shows the temperature dependence of dielectric constant (ϵ') versus temperature of $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ at different frequencies. Strong relaxation of ϵ' is observed in the investigated frequency range where the temperature range is maximum. The dielectric constant increases with temperature increases. The intense peak is observed from the graph between dielectric constant and temperature which corresponds to phase transition temperature (T_m). In this temperature, structural phase transition takes place from polar to non-polar phase at 420 K due to the polarization from two different types of charge carriers^{9,10} for the sample under investigation, the conduction process can be attributed to the presence of two types of charge carriers, that is, p type, as a hole exchange between Co^{3+} and Co^{2+} and transfer of O^{2-} between filled side with vacant oxygen side. Fig. 3(b) shows the temperature dependence of dielectric loss (or) $\tan \delta$ also increases with increasing temperature. The major reason for increasing dielectric loss due to the domain wall density increases resulting in the decrease of the dielectric constant. Fig. 3(c) shows the temperature dependence of σ_{ac} for $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ at a frequency of 500 Hz. The Figure shows that σ_{ac} increases gradually with temperature up to 423 K after which a rapid increase is obtained. The conductivity gets decreases with increased temperature¹¹. The activation energies were calculated by curve fitting eq. (6), the activation energy is $E_a = 0.99$ eV. The low activation energy suggests an intrinsic conduction due to the contribution of space charge carriers and holes. Fig. 3(d) shows the diffuse phase transition graph plot between $\ln(\epsilon'_m/\epsilon')$ vs $\ln(T - T_m)$ at the frequency of 500 Hz can be obtained from the following Vogel-Fulcher eq. (7),

$$\epsilon'_m/\epsilon'(f,T) = 1 + [T - T_m(f)]^\gamma / 2\delta^2 \quad (1 \leq \gamma \geq 2) \quad (7)$$

where ϵ'_m maximum dielectric constant at T_m , T_m is the phase transition temperature, ϵ' dielectric constant, δ is the degree of dielectric relaxation, γ is the degree of diffuseness and T is the absolute temperature in Kelvin. The degree of dielectric relaxation can be obtained from the slope of the graph ($\gamma = 1.02$) is > 1 , express more relax or ferroelectric behaviour of transition. The intercept of the graph is the degree of diffuseness ($\delta = 0.56$) resulted in a lower degree of diffuseness and weaker relaxor behaviour¹².

Fig. 3. (a) Variations of dielectric constant (ϵ') as a function of temperature for $K_{0.5}CoO_2$, (b) variations of dielectric loss ($\tan \delta$) as a function of temperature for $K_{0.5}CoO_2$, (c) variations of AC conductivity versus temperature at a frequency of 500 Hz for $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ and (d) diffuse phase transition graph plot between $\ln(\epsilon'_m/\epsilon')$ vs $\ln(T - T_m)$ at frequency of 500 Hz for $K_{0.5}CoO_2$.

Conclusions

Single phase $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ was synthesized by molten salt method. The phase formation was confirmed by XRD and the results demonstrate that has been used as a better preparation method of cobalt based layered potassium oxide. The advantage of this method is simple low cost and environmental friendly. The scanning electron microscopic studies indicate that agglomerated micro porous sphere and have average grain size 150 to 300 nm. The optical absorption band gap as 2.5 eV it behaves as a semiconducting material. $K_{0.5}CoO_2$ has AC-conductivity observed as the function of temperature indicates the polarization contributes the conduction mechanism. The important parameter such as activation energy $E_a = 0.99$ eV was determined by dielectric studies.

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